

Lesson Plan and Its Importance in Teaching Process

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ABSTRACT: Teaching in the simplest sense of the term is the flow of interaction between the teacher and the students that is done to achieve pre-designed goals based on a codified plan. Planning and goals of a lesson presented by the teacher at the beginning of the session is one of the most important and effective factors in the learning process of students. Summing up these items at the end of the lesson and presenting a summary of a lesson is of special importance to the students' learning. The necessity of developing lesson plans in our classrooms, schools and educational institutions is a case that is less appreciated to it, so this study has been done to investigate how to prepare and implement lesson plan and to know its importance in the teaching process of learning. The resources used in this research are textbooks and curriculum, educational and scientific articles. The findings of this research show that curriculum in the teaching process causes the teacher to be ready for teaching and to formulate his/her course activities according to the students' preparation level.

KEYWORDS: teaching, design, annual lesson plan, daily lesson plan

INTRODUCTION

The lesson plan forms the basis of education. In fact, the lesson plan is the education plan and it plays an essential role in the form of learning. If education is supposed to be based on scientific principles, it is necessary to have a precise plan based on scientific principles. The importance and necessity of a lesson plan is similar to a building plan. Just as a construction engineer designs a plan before building a repair, the teacher should also design an educational plan in which the content of education, teaching method, media and educational aids are predicted and teach according to this plan. Depending on whether the lesson plan is related to the teaching of the desired subject during an academic year or half a year, a month or a day, different types of lesson plans are prepared.

The teacher is considered as one of the important pillars of education, and in the matter of education, not only the way the teacher teaches, but also all of his behaviors are effective in attracting the students' attention and the quality of education. Studies have shown that the teacher is the most effective factor in motivating students to learn. One of the components related to the teacher is his interest in teaching and learning, as well as the observance of educational rules and regulations by the teacher. The findings show that students consider class attendance necessary to understand the subject, but it is the professor's teaching style that determines his effective attendance in the class and the continuation of the course. It is interesting to note that the way of expression, the mastery of the teacher in the teaching the subject, the way of organizing and arranging the lesson, and the enthusiasm to help solve the problems of the students were selected as the characteristics of a good teacher, and the most important criterion of a good teacher was the mastery of the teaching the subject. Achieving an ideal teaching requires strong links between the lesson objectives and the students' teaching and learning methods. Teaching is a group and two-way interactive process, during which the learner and the teacher are both influenced by each other. Teaching the teacher's explicit expression is one of those things that must be learned. The lesson plan is a written description of the education process, in which it is shown what, by what method, at what time and place should be learned and how the students will be evaluated. It should be known that the human capacity for learning is limited and no one can acquire all skills and knowledge (Omidi et al., 2012, p. 109). Therefore, it is necessary for the teacher to plan his teaching process in advance and design it in a codified and documented plan, so that by using this plan, they can turn the teaching-learning flow in an effective way.

The Concept of Teaching

The term "teaching" in educational science texts is one of the topics that all those involved in this field of science are familiar with, but it seems that most of the teachers and presenters of teaching programs are rarely familiar with its true meaning and nature. Teachers' different perceptions of the concept of teaching can leave positive and negative aspects in their attitude towards students

and how to work with them. Differences in perceptions, lack of awareness of views on this topic, or confusion in understanding the concepts of educational sciences, this misinterpretation occurs mostly in concepts such as upbringing, education, teaching and practicum. Although each of the mentioned concepts may complement the other or interfere in terms of nature, they are different in terms of the scope of application and intended purpose. Cultivation is an orderly and systematic process whose purpose is to guide the physical, cognitive, moral, and social development or in general the all-round development of the students' personality in order to acquire and understand human knowledge and the norms accepted by the society and also to help their talents flourish. According to this definition, education is a system whose basic function is to flourish diversity and educate citizens who acquire the norms accepted by the society and are committed to their values.

On the other hand, the concept of education is not opposed to the education of a system, but rather it is the goal-oriented and pre-designed activity education, which aims to provide opportunities and situations that facilitate and speed up learning within an educational system. Therefore, education is a means of schooling, not education itself.

Meanwhile, the concept of teaching refers to that part of the educational activities that happens with the presence of the teacher in the classroom. Teaching is a part of education, and like education, it includes a series of regular, goal-oriented and pre-designed activities, and its purpose is to create favorable learning conditions on the part of the teacher. Based on this definition, teaching itself has a set of characteristics that are mentioned below:

- a. This interaction, which has the form of certain activities, is determined and designed in advance.
- b. Regular design is done according to the location and facilities.
- c. Creating opportunities and facilitating learning in teaching is considered important (Sha'bani, 2011).

Therefore, teaching (teaching) mainly refers to the activities that the teacher performs verbally in the presence of students. In this case, Dembo (1994) has defined teaching as a set of actions that are carried out by the teacher with the intention of helping to create learning. Also, Ednell, Reeve, and Smet (2007) have also defined teaching as interpersonal efforts to help learners acquire knowledge, learn skills, and understand their abilities (Seif, 2015, 36).

In short, it can be said that the teacher's scattered and one-sided activities that may cause a change in the students are not called teaching. That is, the teacher should determine what the purpose of teaching is according to the set of conditions. What capabilities should be developed in students so that educational content can be selected based on them and activities can be designed accordingly.

This is despite the fact that the concept of training (vocational training) has a much more limited meaning than education, training and teaching. The meaning of internship is to give the techniques and skills needed to the trainees to perform a certain job or profession. It means expanding the attitude, knowledge, skills, and behavioral patterns needed by a person to perform a proper function in a certain task or job (Sha'bani, 2011).

Chart (1): Determining the position of teaching among concepts, internship, education, and education (Sha'bani, 2013, p. 12).

According to the above, what is considered important is how the teacher should provide the conditions and situation in which the effectiveness and efficiency of teaching will increase and provide the expected results. Effective teaching is an activity that uses an appropriate combination of theories, motivations, skills, organization, and the art of teaching and training. This type of teaching is not only an intellectual activity that primarily seeks to fulfill cognitive goals, but also a deeply personal, personal, and ethical endeavor.

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- a. Interaction between teacher and student is essential in teaching.
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Teacher and Teaching Process

Bilateral activity or interaction between the teacher and the learner with the aim of learning is called teaching. A basic point of this type of activity is its two-sidedness, which educational psychology will be the foundation of this issue. It has been said that a set of logical and continuous measured actions that a teacher performs in order to present a lesson is called a teaching process.

Teaching itself has three components: First, the joint performance of teachers in teaching all scientific fields, which is the basic component. Second, the teacher's functions that are specific to a certain discipline and are called specific content elements. And third, the concepts that show the performance of the teacher and the flow of learning and growth of the students, which is called the theoretical element.

According to many experts, including Smith (1985), these three topics constitute the basic elements of teaching. Successful teaching cannot be based only on a certain method or approach, but must combine different strategies. It is natural that in the course of teaching, we are faced with different decisions, different personalities, different needs of students and certain strategies. What teachers need is to apply the basic principles to analyze each situation and make appropriate decisions and have a specific and predetermined plan for it (Lutfabadi, 2016).

Teachers, like the art of pioneers, use valid scientific laws in the performance of their special skills, but they do not have a specific prescription for teaching, to combine some things with others, and then claim that the product is teaching. If such a thing was possible, then it would be considered technology teaching and we could train the desired teachers by using only technical skills and predetermined goals. However, there is no prescription that prescribes for teachers and advises them to do it equally for all students and achieve the desired result. On the other hand, research shows that we can determine and prescribe specific behavioral criteria for our teaching, and these factors are not ineffective for their part in teaching and better conclusions, and among them some are superior to others and produce more valuable results (Parsa, 1385).

From the teacher's activities to measure a teaching process, what can be an example of the definition of teaching is to have a predetermined plan for teaching. Therefore, to create this plan, teachers at any level or level of education, before the beginning of teaching, it should answer the following questions:

1. To whom should I teach? (Knowing the students)
2. What should be taught? (Teaching topic)
3. Why do this learning activity? (Teaching purpose)
4. How should I start and do it? (Teaching methods and tools)
5. What activities should I do? (Determining activities)
6. When should I do it? (Timing of activities)
7. What part of that activity will everyone do? (Interaction between teacher and student)
8. How can I make sure that I have reached the desired goals? (Evaluation) (Shaari, 2017)

An expert and experienced teacher, before teaching, thinks about the educational activities of his class and examines the elements involved and influencing it and tries to take advantage of the set of facilities available in the memorization-learning process. But the non-expert and inexperienced teacher starts teaching without thinking about the results and process of educational activities and using the facilities; and this is the difference between the two (Sha'bani, 2011, p. 247). Therefore, the basic structure of this design can be shown in the diagrams below:

Chart (2): process of designing a lesson plan (Shari Nezhad, 1387, p. 616).

Chart (3): Teaching Process Template, (Lutfabadi, 1386, p. 29)

The above diagrams show that teachers need to have a detailed plan to implement teaching, in which it should be clear who they are teaching, what subjects their lesson content includes, how and with what tools teaching should be done, how to ensure that the desired goals are achieved. Therefore, lesson planning and having the skills are considered important for teachers.

Curriculum or Teaching Preparation

From the point of view of education, lesson planning is an activity, preparation of measures for action in the educational process. These measures specify the purpose of the educational action (goals), how the educational action takes place (methods), and how the awareness of the educational scientific effectiveness is obtained (evaluation) (Mousavi-pour, 2013, p. 26). In terms of lexical roots, lesson planning is taken from the Latin word (currere) which means course or the way to be followed. Conceptually, it is a process that leads to a curriculum (Molki, 2013, p. 23). Curriculum has been defined as "a series of predetermined experiences to help learners achieve the main and fundamental goals". This process is usually called "curriculum planning" for the effort that is made in planning the issues and contents of education at the macro level. After analyzing the content of the content, regarding the content to be presented in a specific package in each course or class, as well as the sequence and intervals of the educational experiences that should ultimately bring the learners to the optimal level of the expected qualification (knowledge or skill), A decision is made. The design of a macro-curriculum is usually done in committees composed of teachers, principals and educational experts, which collectively determine the courses that should be chosen by students in an educational course, the content of those

courses, and the priority and delay of each course compared to other courses. They make decisions (Miller, 2013, pp. 28-29). In this topic, what we mean by lesson planning is the same lesson plan that the teacher designs in advance for his teaching. In the book of educational sciences, its nature and scope, according to Eisner, they have expressed the concept of curriculum as follows: "A teacher's curriculum, or a lesson or a class, can be considered a set of pre-planned events aimed at achieving Educational-educational results are considered for one or more students" (Group of Writers, 2015).

The important and key subject of lesson planning is to establish a logical and correct connection between the designed objectives, lesson content, teaching and learning methods, and student learning assessment. At the same time, students' characteristics should always be considered. In the past, many lessons started with vague objectives and teaching methods were used that had little relation to the formulated objectives. The evaluation methods used were either unrelated or had little relation with each of the established goals. Such courses put students in an unfavorable position, which endangers their academic future. The said inappropriate model can be improved by adopting a method that links the objectives with the lesson content, teaching method and evaluation. This importance is achieved when the goals express the expectation that we expect from the students. The teaching method also encourages and supports students to undertake activities to gain the necessary understanding. The task of evaluation is to tell the students what is needed and show whether the goals have been achieved or not (Nasri et al., 2016, p. 162).

Therefore, lesson planning at the macro level, as described in its description, provides teachers with the possibility to prepare at the small level (implementation of the program at the class level). At the elementary level, the responsibility of planning is the responsibility of the teacher. At this level, the teacher should plan the lesson to be taught. Of course, in educational institutions (usually universities), the amount of responsibility given to the teacher in this field is different. For example, an educational institution may determine in advance the course titles, course headings, and the book that should be taught as a textbook and present it to the teacher. In another institution, they may even prepare the teaching structure, including the objective objectives of the different parts of the lesson, the heading of each part, and the teaching methods in advance, that is, they provide the teacher in the form of a textbook, which is common in our schools. We refer to it as "learning packages" in this article.

Learning packages are similar to a curriculum in many ways, except that they are designed and delivered to guide individual students in just one specific area of the material they need to learn. Because learning packages are basically effective in teaching, it can be considered an educational aid that is carefully prepared and guides students while learning the content and details of the lesson. This package provides students with the necessary materials, appropriate time, and sufficient means to achieve mastery in each of the objective objectives set. In general, these learning packages can be referred to as "guides", "learning guides", or "golden models."

Learning packages are prepared and made available in different forms and at different levels of learning. But despite the dispersion and variety of terms used in them, it is mandatory to follow the principles of curriculum preparation for them. Of course, it is possible to go to the class and teach without writing and compiling the program and lesson plan, but if the teacher wants to do his job well, he must write his lesson plan exactly (Miller and Miller, 2013).

Although in our schools, the textbooks usually pre-determine most of the planning actions, but a professional teacher knows that the time he spends on lesson planning is actually an investment that will bring him many benefits in the future. The benefits obtained in this way are:

1. Increase learning
2. Optimum use of the time spent in class
3. Fewer problems in the order of things
4. The increasing improvement of teaching
5. Teacher's peace and comfort

Therefore, it is necessary for teachers to plan personally for each lesson and the participants in each class. Certainly, if the teacher is given the responsibility of planning the entire educational period, his duty to plan and organize the work before the beginning of the educational period is much wider than when he is only assigned to teach a part of the lesson that has already been planned by another teacher, they have been employed. However, it is necessary for every teacher to know the planning process as well as the examples of decisions that must be made in connection with the selection and organization of curriculum content (Miller and Miller, 2013).

It is a fact that planning requires time, knowledge, skill, and patience; And they may become less interested in it after a period of time and develop a negative attitude. Therefore, by observing the following, teachers can do better in planning and teaching effectively and enjoy their teaching:

1. Design your lesson planning just a few weeks before the teaching process, because the existing conditions may change and your planning is no longer suitable for the existing conditions.
2. Before planning, ask yourself what skills and what kind of knowledge the students are going to learn.
3. Make sure that they have clearly stated the teaching goals.
4. They should predict the level of required ability in advance, that is, the prepared program should not only be designed for gifted students, but this design should also include the compatibility of low-level students.
5. To try to make their lesson plan interesting for them by measuring the ability of the students, so that the ground of participation of all the students is provided.
6. Using by recounting the material learned by the students to other students, to ensure the success rate of their curricula, which would lead to interest in the teacher.
7. Use themes and subjects related to the lesson.
8. Plan the timetable for achieving the goals. For this, the most suitable method is to try to teach most of the subjects in the first half of the year so that the students can review the material at the end of the year (Brawn et al., 2012).

Lesson Plan

Education scientists are believed the opinion that good teaching requires a good planning and this plan must be determined in advance (Frotan, 2007, p. 200). Teaching without a pre-planned program is a blind work and designing without implementation is a fruitless activity that will only adorn the pages of paper (Sha'bani, 2011, p. 247). In simple words, the lesson plan is a plan that the teacher prepares to create effective learning in the students (Aghazadeh, 2014, p. 235). In other words; The lesson plan is a teacher's guide and a regular and organized framework for educational events (Sha'bani, 2011, p. 247).

Or the lesson plan consists of planning and organizing the activities that the teacher and students do on the way to achieve the learning goals. The lesson plan actually deals with how to organize and present the material in a way that has a logical form so that a topic is conveyed to the students in an appropriate way. The existential philosophy of the lesson plan, which is also called educational design or textbook... is one of the skills before teaching and one of the most important skills of the teaching profession. perform and realize a special organization in his activities (Molki, 2013).

In a well-organized lesson plan, at least elements and structures such as lesson topic, Russian content, general goal, partial and behavioral goals, students' input behavior, diagnostic evaluation, educational activities, teaching method, required educational tools, evaluation method at the end of the lesson should be included, and supplementary activities outside the guild (factory) are examined and paid attention to. The lesson plan should be set in such a way that even a beginner teacher can implement his educational activities in the class with an overview (Sha'bani, 2011, pp. 247-248). In order for the lesson plan to be formed, the teacher must first think about the purpose of the lesson, then he must consider the content of the lesson. Since in our country, the lesson content is presented in the form of textbooks, the teacher does not have any particular difficulty in preparing the lesson content. In fact, the content is the same as in the students' textbook. The third issue that the teacher should evaluate is the teaching method. The teaching method is determined based on the goal and volume of the content. The next thing is the time and materials and tools needed to prepare the learning conditions, which should be determined and prepared in advance. After the mentioned cases, the teacher should determine the way of acting in the class. The way of working in the class is determined based on the teaching method. For example, if the teaching method is the role-playing method, the action method will be adjusted based on the stages of the role-playing method (Aqazadeh, 2014). For more clarification, the above items can be presented in the form of the following questions, and upon receiving the appropriate answers, teachers can proceed to lesson design:

1. What position do I want to teach (today, this session)?
2. What purpose do I want to teach?
3. How long should I teach?
4. Who do I want to teach?
5. What method should I use to teach better?

6. Which educational tools can I use for teaching?
7. What activity should everyone (teacher-student) do?
8. How can I know that I have reached my goals?

By providing the answers to the above questions, the teaching-learning flow for teachers is determined. Once the topic of discussion is determined, they evaluate their information. If they have a special problem regarding the topic of the lesson from a scientific point of view, they can solve the problem by referring to reliable sources. Searching for the answer to the second question provides the possibility for teachers to think about the effects of the discussed topic on the class and students, that is, what is the purpose of the effort in the class? And where should they reach and what will be realized? The third question defines the time period in which teachers should realize their desired goal and make it practical. Consideration of teaching time by a teacher should be taken seriously. Because one of the most important things in the teaching-learning process is the time limit. Time is limited in two ways. One is in terms of the duration of students' ability to listen, learn, act, etc., because; the power and potential of students is limited. The other is about the hour that each lesson is assigned in the weekly schedule and no teacher can change it.

There are teachers who implement almost all the necessary skills in teaching, but they are faced with extra time, and there are teachers who have not yet implemented some of the teaching skills, the lesson ends and they are faced with a lack of time. In fact, both groups of teachers have problems with time management. In response to the fourth question, teachers actually have a serious view of their audience. They pay attention to their audience from multiple dimensions, that is, they must consider them from different developmental, social, cultural, etc. dimensions. Thinking about the teaching method provides this opportunity to the teachers to determine the best method to implement it by mastering the topic of discussion. By defining the teaching method, teachers can choose tools and equipment that can be used to make the lesson more objective.

The answer to the next question is quantitative to the teachers that, in the teaching process according to the nature of the subject and the teaching materials, which of the teachers and students should display specific activities, and how and how the quantity and quality of these activities should be done by the teachers. Adjust before starting the lesson. Finally, the answer to the last question provides teachers with this context, which informs them of reaching the goals. That is, they determine the evaluation methods of the lesson in advance (Molki, 2013). Diagram number (4) shows the lesson plan process.

Chart (4): Process of Lesson Plan

The Importance and Necessity of the Lesson Plan in Teaching Process

So far, it has happened that teachers who have designed their lesson well and spent the necessary effort in preparing it have not done bad teaching. But contrary to many, it has been seen that even the best trainee teachers and the best trainers have not been able to provide a good lesson to the students without having a lesson plan. Not having a lesson plan prevents the teacher from incorrectly

implementing the necessary actions. Having a lesson plan helps the teacher to examine how to get into the material and various possibilities (Frotan, 2017, p. 200). Of course, without a curriculum and writing a lesson plan, you can manage the classroom activities, but a well-written lesson plan enables the teacher to think regularly and systematically during the training course, and all the effective factors in the teaching-learning process checking before the process (Sha'bani, 2011). In summary, the following points are the importance of the lesson plan in the teaching process:

- ✦ By using the lesson plan, teachers are able to access the lesson content more efficiently.
- ✦ By using the lesson plan, teachers can predict the appropriate methods of teaching the content and prepare to implement it.
- ✦ Preparation of lesson plans help teachers to be prepared in advance on the parts of the content that they do not have control over.
- ✦ Preparation of the lesson plan provides the inclusion of all the lesson content and prevents forgetting part of the content.
- ✦ The lesson plan makes the teachers innovative and creative in the implementation of activities.
- ✦ The lesson plan allows the allocation of time, means and facilities to the set of goals according to the importance of each event (Molki, 2013).
- ✦ The lesson plan determines the learning experiences more accurately.
- ✦ Assignments and supplementary activities are determined more carefully.
- ✦ In preparing exam questions and evaluating educational activities, educational goals are not forgotten (Sha'bani, 2013).

Types of Lesson Plans

In terms of nature, teachers usually do lesson planning in two ways: some prepare mental lesson plans, and others prepare written lesson plans. Both of the mentioned measures are useful and beneficial for creating an effective environment for learning. Although there is no specific preference for using any of the two types of subjective and objective lesson plans, but in terms of documenting actions to create learning opportunities, it is recommended to use written or objective lesson plans. And in terms of form, in the past it was thought that the teacher should write different types of lesson plans, for example, daily, weekly, monthly, quarterly and annual lesson plans, nowadays such an idea is not liked (Aghazadeh, 2014).

Today, what is more acceptable is that teachers should use two types of curriculums; One annual lesson plan and the second daily lesson plan to design their teaching process. By preparing an annual plan, teachers determine the plans to achieve the general learning goals that are expected to be realized in the form of a subject during one academic year. The lesson plan is a written and considered program that the teacher prepares for a lesson before teaching (Molki, 2013).

Annual Lesson Plan and How to Prepare It

The annual lesson plan is a document that shows what activities the teacher will do during an academic year and at what time. The annual lesson plan is usually prepared at the beginning of the academic year, that is, before the start of the official flow of the course and after the division of topics in the division of time is done based on the educational plan. The annual lesson plan is prepared based on the following information and measures:

1. Use the division of school hours to determine how many lessons per week the desired topic should be taught.
2. Determine how many pages the textbook has.
3. Using the calendar, calculate that from the beginning of the academic year (Month of Aries) to the end of the academic year (Month of Scorpio), how many sessions should be attended to teach that subject.
4. From the yearbook, it should be determined precisely which days of the week this topic is taught, which days are public holidays and schools are closed.
5. A few lessons should be added to it based on the default among the teacher's legal holidays.
6. The number of school weeks and school days that the teacher should teach should be determined using the above information.
7. The number of subjects and pages of the book should be divided into the number of teaching hours based on its objectives.
8. Based on the division of lesson time into book topics, the lesson plan table should be set.
9. Objectives and complementary activities should be determined for each subject. "These items can be optional because they can be determined in the daily curriculum as well" (Molki, 2013).

Table (1): Template No. (1) the Schedule of the Annual Lesson Plan (Sha'bani, 2013, p. 250)

Subject:		Class:	Teacher:	Academic Year:	General Learning Objectives	
Months	Weeks	Date	Chapters	Lesson Title	General Obj.	Activities
March	Week 1	Session 1				
	Week 2	Session 2				
	Week 3	Session 3				
	Week 4	Session 4				
April	Week 1	Session 5				
	Week 2	Session 6				
	Week 3	Session 7				
	Week 4	Session 8				
May	Week 1	Session 9				
	Week 2	Session 10				
	Week 3	Session 11				
	Week 4	Session 12				
June	Week 1	Session 13				
	Week 2	Session 14				
	Week 3	Session 15				
	Week 4	Session 16				

The above plan is presented only for the first four months of the academic year and the following months of the year can be added to the table.

Sample of Annual Lesson Plan

Table (2): Template no. (2) is the Annual Lesson Plan

Month	Hamal	Saor	Jawza	Saratan	Assad	Sonbla	Mizan	Aqrab	Qous	Total
Days of the Month	31	31	31	31	31	31	30	30	30	276
Fridays	4	5	4	4	4	4	5	4	4	38
General Holidays	1	1	0	0	1	3	0	3	0	9
Teacher Holiday	2	2	2	1	0	2	1	2	0	12
Exam Days	0	0	0	15	0	0	0	0	15	30
Warming Vocation	0	0	0	0	15	0	0	0	0	15
teaching Days	24	23	25	10	10	22	24	21	0	159
Number of Weeks	4	4	4	2	2	4	4	3	2	29
Teaching Hrs/ Week	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	0	16
No. of Teaching Hrs./ Month	8	8	8	4	4	8	8	6	0	54

Chapters and Titles	First chap. and quarter of 2 nd chap.	One Third of 2 nd chapter	3 rd chap and half of the 4 th chap	The rest of the 4 th chap	Chap 5 and quarter of chap 6	Chapter 6	Chapter 7	The rest of the chapter 7	0	7
No. of pgs. per Month	Chap one 8 pgs. Chap two 6 pgs.	24 pages	Chap three 13 pgs. Chap four 8	12 pgs.	Chap five 6 pgs. Chap six 6 pgs.	17 pgs.	18 pgs.	Rest of chap seven 10	0	120
No. of needy lesson hrs.	First chap 12 hrs. quarter of 2 nd 4 hrs.	8 hrs.	Chap three 6 hrs. and chap six 2 hrs.	4 hrs.	Chap five 2 hrs. chap six 2 hrs.	8 hrs.	8 hrs.	6 hrs.	0	54

Teacher: Kankash School: Mawlana Balkhi Class: 9th Subject: Biology Academic Year: 1390

In this model, the annual plan has considered the subject of biology in such a way that two-hours lesson are allocated to it in a week and it has been adjusted according to the information already shared.

Daily Lesson Plan and How to Prepare It

The most important and effective teaching management is having a daily lesson plan. The daily lesson plan is a written and considered plan that the teacher prepares for a lesson before teaching (Safavi, 2014, p. 293). After preparing the annual plan, it is time for the teacher to prepare the daily lesson plan. The daily lesson plan includes predicting and setting up a set of activities that the teacher prepares in advance to achieve one or more educational goals in a lesson. The lesson plan causes the teacher to carry out educational activities in order one after the other in specific stages and times in a logical way, and to base the results of his subsequent activities. In fact, educational design causes the organization and constant evaluation of teaching-learning activities. Because during the implementation of the curriculum, sometimes, a lot of time and energy is wasted due to repetitive activities, or the deliberate omission of some essential materials, due to the lack of time, damages the teaching process. Its most important educational function is that it prevents the repetition of useless materials and activities and the omission of essential items (Sha'bani, 2013, pp. 253-254).

In order to prepare a daily lesson plan, several plans have been proposed according to different points of view, but what is certain is that a completely standard and uniform form that is accepted by everyone cannot be considered (Molki, 2013). For example, some have tried to present it in a simpler way in which they are satisfied with the following:

- ✍ Issue
- ✍ Class
- ✍ Target
- ✍ Method
- ✍ Time
- ✍ Required materials and liquids (Aghazadeh, 2014).

But to prepare an effective daily lesson plan, the following twelve steps can be followed:

1. Determining the general characteristics: including the subject of the lesson, desired class, teaching time, teaching date, school name, and teacher's name.
2. Determining the subject or title of the lesson: The title of the lesson must be precise and clear
3. Determining learning goals, (general, partial and behavioral goals): goals should be determined according to the principles and techniques of classification of cognitive, emotional, and skill goals.
4. Determining verbal or pre-learned behavior goals and how to test them: By preparing students' verbal behavioral goals, the teacher must prepare diagnostic evaluation questions (starters).
5. Selection of educational materials and tools or media: Media is a tool that creates communication between the sender and the receiver and facilitates the teaching process, so teachers should follow it in their plan.
6. Determining preliminary tasks: Normally, the teacher should do preliminary tasks before starting teaching, such as attendance and absence, checking homework and ensuring the physical and mental health of students, as well as giving necessary reminders. Of course, you should not spend a lot of time on this step.
7. Determining the content and method of preparation and motivation for learning: The teacher should consider a method to create interest in learning in his lesson plan. During an introduction, he should create motivation to motivate and enthusiasm for learning, prepare them to pay attention and learn the lesson.
8. Determining the step-by-step presentation of the new lesson: consider the steps of presenting the new lesson in the form of a list of basic tasks that must be done in the class, because it is considered necessary to write them in the lesson plan, not in a detailed way, but in a summary way.
9. Determining lesson activities: At this stage, teachers should determine the activities of themselves and their students at the beginning, during and after the teaching process, according to their lesson content.
10. Determining the appropriate methods in the teaching process: teachers should predict the most appropriate method or methods for implementation in the teaching method column, according to the set goals and activities mentioned in the content presentation.
11. Determining the method of ending the lesson and evaluation after presenting the new lesson: The teachers must have prepared the summary of the lesson in a precise way in their plan to present it to the students at the end of the lesson. These stages can be done by the teacher or the students in an explanatory way or by presenting questions and answers. That this work of self-evaluation is also considered as part of the teaching process.
12. Compensatory and supplementary activities (homework): After evaluating and identifying the weak points of students' learning, the teacher should consider compensatory activities and exercises for weak students as well as extensive and supplementary activities for strong students in his plan. And it can also predict activities outside the classroom to strengthen the material learned in the classroom and relate it to the real performance of the students (Sha'bani, 2011, Safavi, 2014, Frotan, 2017).

Using the above steps, two examples of the daily plan are presented:

Table (3): Template number (1), day lesson plan (Molki, 1393, p. 25)

Teaching Process	Suggested Activities	Time
Activities before starting the lesson		
Presenting the lesson like chart		
Recognition / Starting Evaluation		
Getting ready /motivate the students		
Presenting the new lesson		
Summarizing the lesson lengthily		
Reading the in terms of necessity		
Final evaluation		
Giving home assignment for next session		
Evaluation of learning outcomes		
Analysis of the evaluation		
Determining the completion activities		

Chart (4): Template Number (2) Daily Lesson Plan

DISCUSSION

Education planning, however, is a process that guides the flow of education activities and this process is carried out by a group of experts; But what can achieve its results is its implementation by the executors of these programs (teachers), which is achieved through the teaching process. Although the effective factors of the learner are numerous, what seemed important is how teachers can turn the classroom into a teaching-learning process. Therefore, it is necessary to foresee all the goals, activities, use of tools and equipment that can facilitate this process.

In centralized educational systems that have the same curriculum content and present it in a compiled form at the country level, most of the curriculum planning measures (lesson plan) are presented in the form of textbooks. However, teachers who want to get better results from the teaching process, it is considered important to plan their lessons in advance, because; Classroom conditions, prevailing social factors, students' status, etc. are among the variables that depend on special situations and cannot be considered in the textbooks.

Although teachers usually adjust their lesson plans in a mental way and this can also be beneficial, but various factors may lead to them not being able to pay attention to each and every activity considered and unintentionally or intentionally forgetting part of the Embed content and anticipated activities. Therefore, having a written and documented plan helps them to compensate for this deficiency. Lesson design is usually done in two ways, which are known as annual lesson plan and daily lesson plan. In the annual lesson plan, the teacher usually tries to design a general plan to achieve the goals of an academic course in advance, taking into account the time, facilities and conditions, and imagine it briefly for himself. However, the daily lesson plan gives the teacher the opportunity to predict the details of his work and activities using the annual lesson plan, to determine his work method and lesson activities in advance, and to pre-determine how he will study the lesson content. Finally, the lesson plan (daily or yearly) for the teacher can act as a guide and provide the context to prevent deviation and make the teaching-learning process interesting and acceptable for the learners.

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